

LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECTS OF THE STUDY OF WORD MEANING

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Annotation: In this research work we can focus on linguocultural aspects of the study of word meaning and scientific ideas of the world, the formation of linguocultural background or worldview, mythological worldview, process of cognition. The system of concepts expressed in language expresses such a complex relationship of concepts that their complex use allows to convey the content of human thought in different ways, that is, using simple and descriptive definitions.

Key words: linguocultural aspect, cognition, formation, scientific perception

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ishida so'z ma'nosi va dunyo ilmiy g'oyalarini o'rganishning lingvomadaniy jihatlari, lingvomadaniy fon yoki dunyoqarashning shakllanishi, mifologik dunyoqarash, bilish jarayoniga e'tibor qaratishimiz mumkin. Tilda ifodalangan tushunchalar tizimi tushunchalarning shunday murakkab munosabatini ifodalaydiki, ulardan kompleks foydalanish inson tafakkuri mazmunini turli yo'llar bilan, ya'ni sodda va tavsiflovchi ta'riflar yordamida etkazish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvomadaniy jihat, bilish, shakllanish, ilmiy idrok

Аннотация: В данной исследовательской работе мы можем сосредоточить внимание на лингвокультурных аспектах изучения значения слова и научных представлений о мире, формировании лингвокультурного фона или мировоззрения, мифологического мировоззрения, процесса познания. Система понятий, выраженная в языке, выражает столь сложную взаимосвязь понятий, что их комплексное употребление позволяет передавать содержание человеческой мысли разными способами, т. е. с помощью простых и описательных определений.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурный аспект, познание, формирование, научное восприятие.

The conceptual worldview is an essential condition for the life activities of a person who is biosocial. Throughout his conscious life, man repeatedly refers

to, uses, accepts, contributes to, and perfects the categories of conceptual worldviews. (See Ufimieva N.V. 1996, Yakovenko E.B. 1999, Chomsky N.1968).

The formation of a linguoculturological background or worldview is a long historical process that has come a long way from the primitive archaic stage to the modern scientific stage. In the distant past, our ancestors were far from the current scientific theory of the world and its creation. The mythological worldview of different peoples is an example of this.

M.Khalikova divides the essence of worldviews formed on the basis of linguocultural knowledge into several types;

- worldview formed through the personal experience of each person;
- Linguistic worldview formed within a certain language;
- a conceptual worldview that is unique to all individuals.

The national character of the worldview, as we have noted above, is due to its limitation within a particular language. The metaphors, stereotypes, and standards that permeate every linguocultural community lead to a feature that is unique to only one language. For example, to know well, the meaning is expressed in Uzbek, Czech and French as "to know like five paws", "to know like one's own pocket", "to know like one's own boots".

Thus, there is a complex and infinitely ongoing relationship between the linguoculturological background, the model, and the conceptual picture, i.e., the understanding of the world within a particular language and the general worldview.

In order to unite the national with specific, subjectively meaningful universal concepts, it is necessary to go through intermediate stages, that is, the need to transform the "internal model" into a "universal model" requires some kind of intellectual transformation phase. According to L. Weiserberg, linguistic meaning plays the role of an intermediate world. (See Ashurova D.U.2003, Boboxonova L.G.1995, Boduen de Kurtene 1993, Vejbitskaya A.1997).

According to V.A. Zvegintsev, "The process of cognition is the activity of this thought, which is aimed at creating an internal model of the world given by experience in the mind. At this point, language objectifies this model in the process of communication activity, making it the basis of communication. Semantic meaning arises as a result of the act of thinking. Through it, man communicates this or that with his inner world, and through language, he communicates with other people's inner models. In this way a linguistic model of the world observed in this or that language emerges.

Where there is no historical or factual material, some researchers claim that "man first linguistically systematized the experience he gained by observing and seeing beings," and they try to prove this idea by the mythological material that exists in world languages and the material of underdeveloped languages.

The model of scientific perception, which is closely connected with the knowledge of the objective being, consists of a transitional stage, followed by the artistic expression of the being, which indicates that the language is fully formed. References to history should serve as one of the arguments used to confirm, reinforce the general idea in these cases. (See Vinogradov V.V. 2003, Wolf E.M. 2002, Vorobev V.V. 1996, Gak V.G. 1977, Gaffarova G. 1997)

In this case, language must manifest itself as the creator of its own lingvoculturological model, and as a result it must become an independent force of "linguistic cognition". This is inconsistent with the assertion that the original judgment is the material form of consciousness. The subjective nature of language becomes the decisive force of cognition, and its structure turns out to be immanent, inherently hereditary, innate. It is aimed at creating and transmitting information, thoughts, knowledge about an objective being. The language system itself contains this linguistic commonality that arises in the process of knowing existence.

The system of concepts expressed in language expresses such a complex relationship of concepts that their complex use allows to convey the content of human thought in different ways, that is, using simple and descriptive definitions. This is the peculiarity of language, that is, language is a tool for the formation of thought, language can be not only a means of storing knowledge, but also a way of expressing it with the dynamics of its development. From a semantic point of view, different national languages are different variants of the nominal structure of "universal concepts", a potentially unique universal culture - a whole of civilization. (see; Guhman M.M. 1985, Demkov V.Z. 1994, Djusupov N.2006, Karaulov Y.1972)

The system of language, which manifests itself as a system of signs of self-regulation, dual character, and which serves to form and convey thought in its complex application, cannot be regarded as a "linguistic image of being." Knowledge creates the image of the world, not language.

A more rigorous approach to this, the presented image can only be created ideally using full text, i.e. universal language. Knowledge of the conceptual systems of national languages cannot be simplified in terms of the "accuracy of the results. These systems, on the other hand, are considered to be different

variants of a single universal human language, and their content is historically flawed. (See; Karasik V.I. 2001, Kibrik A.A. 1994, Kubryakova E.S. 1994, Lakof Dj. 1987, Lebedeva L.A. 1999, Lukyanova N.A 1986)

In this regard, the solution of lingvoculturological problems cannot be said to have been methodologically correct by the attempts to compare separate language event events isolated from different languages (which was especially often done by B. Warf and his followers). Here, basically, two serious mistakes are made, which are not difficult to perceive not only by an expert who has studied the problem in depth, but also by an ordinary reader. These are:

b) The first mistake is to try to compare the facts of the studied language not with the system of concepts, but directly with the existing things in the material being.

c) The second error is the analysis of this or that unit or form in the language outside the language system, in other words, the analysis does not involve the scope of the complex mechanism of language. aside.

The first mistake leads the authors to the conclusion that "there is a lingvoculturological model of the world". In fact, the linguist had to show the peculiarities of concrete forms in a general language system capable of expressing any concept.

The second error distorts the essence of language, denying that language can be analyzed as a whole system, in which only parts of the language are systematically analyzed and unreasonably compared to other languages. and the Uzbeks have not been able to fit this concept into their minds, or the Uzbek perception and thinking have never encountered this thing before.

When words in two or more languages are compared in some way, and when there is a mismatch of meanings, linguists come to the "universal" conclusion that "the conceptual apparatus of peoples who speak different languages is different."

It is incorrect to equate the additional national subjective information brought in by the lexical model of language with the specific information brought by the language into the linguistic landscape of the world according to the Sepir-Wharf hypothesis. because the lexical model of language has been associated not only with the lexical but also with the grammatical aspect within this hypothesis. Therefore, the information expressed by grammatical means cannot be excluded from the information entered by the lexical model of the language.

Many researchers repeatedly refer to linguoculturology and the Sepir-Wharf hypothesis. But they can find neither theoretical nor experimental evidence to serve his defense. Well-known scientist E. Lenneberg, concluding the discussion of the experimental study of the Sepir-Wharf hypothesis, was forced to conclude that "there is very little evidence of a violent judgment on the knowledge of the word".

The results of experiments conducted in the field, as well as concrete practical research in this area, show that the Sepir-Wharf hypothesis does not correspond to reality in its classical form.

National identity should be sought not in the linguistic description of the world, but in the specificity of human cognitive activity, which is closely linked to various geographical, historical, production-related, and many other factors. (See: Tukhtasinov I. 2004, Umarov E. 1995, Urison E.V. 2003, Fedoryuk A.V.2001, Hakimova G. 2008, Hammatova A.Sh. 1999, Kharitonchik Z.A.1986, Cheyf U.L. .1975, Shomaqsudov A. 1983)

It should be noted that the logical-philosophical analysis of the problem of national identity of language and its lingvoculturological model in relation to the human worldview remains rather speculative and does not help to draw any clear conclusions from the theoretical study of the problem of national language-folk thinking. But psycholinguistic analysis of speech confirms the specificity of language as an isomorphic process of consciousness. But it does not prove that language plays a dictatorial role in thinking.

In such cases, the various hypotheses that often arise in the process of translating from one language to another, as well as the loss of the "psyche" of the language in translation, are often cited as evidence of the above hypothesis. All of them are methodologically incorrect, because the method of proof cannot be applied to language, and because the information given at the entrance and at the exit belongs to different layers and scales, it contradicts the basic logical rules for the correctness of judgments. For example, the fact that there is an article in German does not mean that Germans accept objects according to some gender-related features.

The Uzbek and Russian words "kol" are pronounced with the English words "hand", "arm", the Uzbek words "kaptar" and "musicha" are given with the same German word "taube". may not lead to the conclusion that the bird cannot be separated from each other. Because in practice, the Germans do the same thing as the Uzbeks do the difference between pigeons and music. (See:

Maslova V.A.2004, Muslenko V.P. 1989, Mirtojiev M.2008, Matyakubov J.I.1996, Ne'matov X.1995, Oparina E.O.1999, Rodionova S.E. 1992, Radchenko G .I. 2007)

The fact that the word "know" in Uzbek is given with the German verbs "wissen" and "kennen" does not mean that Germans know more than Uzbeks, or understand different types of knowledge. Which of the following determines the nature of the relationship between language and thinking? Language or thinking? In answering the question, most people answer "thinking". But some answer "language". If the ratio is 90/10, then Sepir and his followers make up 10%. However, minorities do not always turn out to be wrong.

In our opinion, both language and thinking have their own logic, and this logic distinguishes languages from each other. The thinking among nations is the same, its logic is the same. The language of the peoples is different and the logic of the language in them is also different. The word logic defines selection. Logic is defined by thinking. So, thinking is primary.

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